

Utilization of Electronic Information Resources by Users in Academic Libraries in Maiduguri Metropolitan, Borno State, Nigeria

Ibrahim Sanda Izge
Ramat Library, University of Maiduguri

Emmanuel. M. K. Dawha
Department of Library and Information Science, University of Maiduguri, Borno State.

Samaila Inuwa
Department of Library and Information Science, University of Maiduguri, Borno State.

Abstract

Keywords
Utilization,
Electronic,
Information,
Resources, user's,
Academic,
Libraries
Maiduguri,
Metropolis

Introduction: This study examined the utilization of electronic information resources by users in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolitan, Borno State, Nigeria.

Objectives: The study established three objectives such as to determine the level of utilization of electronic databases by users in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State; to assess the extent of internet utilization by users in these libraries, and to evaluate the extent of use of electronic information resources by users in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State.

Method: Three research questions were formulated to guide the study. A review of related literature was conducted based on the study variables. A survey design was employed, targeting all registered library users of Ramat Library (University of Maiduguri), Professor Babagana Umara Zulum Library (Ramat Polytechnic Maiduguri), and Mohammed Lawan Library (College of Agriculture, Maiduguri), with a total population of 15,238. Using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table for determining sample size, 375 users were sampled. Data collection was conducted via questionnaires, and descriptive statistics, including frequency count and percentage, were used for data analysis.

Results/Findings: The findings indicated that the level of utilization of electronic databases by users was moderate in the academic libraries studied. The extent of internet utilization by users was also found to be moderate.

Conclusion/Recommendations: The study recommends that the management of academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State should provide free internet connectivity to facilitate the searching of information resources by users to a higher extent.

Introduction

The emergence of information explosion and revolution world over has greatly changed the traditional academic library practices and services to some extent. Academic libraries are now repositioning their responsibilities from custodians of traditional information resources to the providers (bread winner) of service oriented digital information resources (electronic materials). Libraries, as reservoirs of knowledge and repositories of information resources are charged with the primary responsibility of serving the diverse needs of its clientele through the provision of adequate information resources. The rapid emergence and advancement in Information and Communication technology (ICT) has brought about revolutionary changes in services and information provision in libraries (Toteng, Hoskins and Bell, 2013). New dimensions in the information generation, acquisition, organization and dissemination in the virtual environment have been introduced. Resources have been produced and repackaged in various ways to meet the needs of information users. One of such ways of repackaging information to satisfy information need is the use of Electronic databases (Obiamalu, Ogunbeni and Obuezie, 2021)

Electronic databases have become an established component of many academic libraries' collection. A large compilation and regularly updated file of digitized information (bibliographic records, abstracts, full-text documents, directory entries, images, statistics, etc.) related to a specific subject field, consisting of records and uniformly organized for ease and speed of search and retrieval and managed with the aid of Database Management System (Kumar, 2016). Electronic databases are widely available and can be accessed from anywhere and by many users at the same time. The content of electronic databases are revised and/or augmented, usually on regular basis, to

provide current information or to add recently published resources and also designed to provide information about a very specific topic, as opposed to a range of topics, usually for a limited audience. It is very appropriate and economical that these databases are optimally utilized to contribute to academic achievement of students and faculty and also to get value for money (Kwadzo, 2015).

Electronic information resources (EIR) have been defined by Obaseki, Oye and Mamman (2012), as information resources which are accessible electronically through computer associated technologies. The setup of the resources could be music, journals, books newspapers, films etc. also, scholarly materials in online database, electronic journals, electronic articles, electronic mail, messages, sources from web pages, online news group posting and newsletters Government publications in electronic formats.

Electronic journals, also known as e-journals and electronic serials, are scholarly journals or intellectual magazines that can be accessed via electronic transmission. In practice, this means that they are usually published in the Web. However, in this modern age of technology, one can assume that almost everybody has access to e-journals due to the diversification of internet in our libraries. One only needs to have access to any piece of technology which allows them the ability to surf the web such as computers, personal digital assistant or commonly known as PDA, mobile phones which is considered to be an essential item for our every-day living nowadays (Ariffin & Bakar, 2013). Together with this presumption of the ease of accessibility of the internet, one could also presume that it is not only logical that all academicians; lecturers and students, are able to easily use this advantage for their academic purposes but should also greatly integrate this technological advancement of e-journals into all of their scholarly publications.

Utilization is the deed of making useful and effective use of library databases and e-resources. Utilization of electronic information resources refers to the act of making practical and fruitful use of the obtainable electronic information resources for academic activities. Utilization is a way in which electronic resources can be located, accessed and retrieved for academic activities. It is expected that if electronic resources are being provided by academic libraries, users should be able to utilize the resources so as to encourage libraries to subscribe to more electronic resources to support teaching and learning process. The use of Electronic Information Resources (EIRs) is necessary for library users mainly because they provide better, faster and easier access to information than information accessed through print media (Nisha and Ali, 2013).

However, under-utilization of electronic information resources hinders the maximization of their academic and research potential, despite significant investments in these resources. This under-utilization may be attributed to various factors such as limited awareness and knowledge of available electronic resource, insufficient information literacy skills to effectively locate and use electronic resources as well as technical issues and accessibility barriers. This study aims to investigate the utilization of electronic information resources by users in academic in Maiduguri Borno State, Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Academic libraries have integrated electronic resources into their collections to promote utilization. However, Users often encounter difficulties in accessing electronic information resources due to limited availability of computer terminals, poor internet connectivity, and insufficient technical infrastructure. Moreover, many users are not fully aware of the available electronic resources or lack the necessary skills to effectively utilize them. This

includes a lack of training and support on how to navigate and use these resources. In the academic libraries under study, poor maintenance of electronic resources and frequent technical problems may hinder the effective use of electronic information resources. This includes outdated software, hardware failures, and insufficient information technology support. There is often inadequate institutional support in terms of funding and policy framework to promote the use of electronic information resources. This limits the availability and quality of electronic resources provided by academic libraries. User attitude and perceptions are also issues in utilization of electronic information resources. Many users still prefer traditional print resources over electronic ones due to familiarity and ease of use.

This preference can limit the adoption and utilization of electronic information resources in academic settings. Preliminary observation conducted by the researcher through interaction with the library users of the academic libraries under study disclosed that the academic libraries have acquired electronic information resources such as e-databases (ARDI, OARE, EBSCO, HINARI), internets, e-journals and e-books which seems to be underutilized to a large extent. This underutilization results in inefficient use of library resources, reduced quality of research and academic output, limited access to up-to-date information and knowledge, inadequate preparation of students for research and professional careers as well as inefficient use of library budget and resources. However, it is against this background that the researcher carried out the study on the utilization of electronic information resources by users in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolitan, Borno State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to determine;

- i. the level of utilization of electronic databases by users' in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State
- ii. the extent of internet utilization by users' in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State.
- iii. the extent of use electronic information resources by users in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following questions;

1. What is the level of utilization of electronic databases by users' in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State?
2. What is the extent of Internet utilization by users' in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State?
3. What is the extent of use electronic information resources by users in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State?

Literature Review

Utilization of Electronic Databases by Users' in Academic Libraries

Some related study have been carried out in the area on utilization of electronic database. Library website resources include electronic books, electronic journals, digital collections, multimedia, etc. Notwithstanding their potential, there have been differing findings on the level of students' access to and use of the

resources. For example, Mutani (2016) examined the utilization of library resources at Saint Augustine University (SAUT) in Tanzania, focusing on how often users utilize the available library resources. It was found that users' utilization of library resources was very low. Elsewhere, Madondo et al. (2017) assessed the usage of electronic information resources by students at Africa University, Zimbabwe. The findings indicate that there was low usage of electronic information resources by students in the study area.

Similarly, Zarghani et al. (2015) attribute the inadequate use of electronic libraries to a lack of awareness about their existence. Moyo (2004) insinuates that inadequate information literacy and technological literacy skills and competencies on the part of library users and the librarians offering the services hinder the effective exploitation of the resources and services available to them in the electronic environment. Madondo et al. (2017) observed that electronic information resources were substantially underutilized by students at the University of Namibia's Northern Campus due to a shortage of computers, unreliable internet connections, and a lack of information literacy skills. In addition, Habiba and Chowdhury (2018) noted that other problems encountered by users when using e-resources include a limited number of titles available, limited access to back issues, difficulty finding relevant information, inability to be accessed from home, slow download speed, and limited access to computers.

Dukper, Sakibu & Arthur (2018) reported a low level of awareness of electronic resources among students with 61% unaware of the availability, 37% used the electronic resources once a week and 31% used it twice a week. Mandale (2019) examined the use of e-resources in Ayurved Medical College Libraries in Maharashtra. It was revealed that on daily basis, students use e-journal at an average of 12 hours per week. In a separate

study in Ghana, Akuffo (2019) and Ankrah & Acheampong (2017) revealed that students use electronic resources for research and assignments. However, Daramola (2016) reported low use of electronic resources among undergraduates in the Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria

Internet Utilization by users' in Academic Libraries

Some related studies have been carried out in the area of internet use. Internet has become the norm and culture of many libraries especially academic libraries. This is because of its drive in higher institution to promote the use of information and communication technology (ICT) to provide educationist, scientist, lecturers and students' access to sources of information at any point over the globe. According to Ikegwuro (2017), internet has become a basic ingredient of information accessibility and dissemination. It is one of the greatest recent advancement in world of information technology and has become a useful instrument that has fostered the process of making the world a global village. Agada and Tofi (2021) noted that internet has impacted on every sphere of academic library activity especially in the form of the library collection development strategies, library building and consortia.

Internet has increasingly become an important source of academic information that has been integrated in the overall services that library offers which ranges from providing books and other informative materials such as current awareness service, selective dissemination of information among others. Atanda (2017) noted that the library and the internet are being viewed increasingly as a versatile unified system, providing an enormous variety of materials in different formats. The internet has become an important subject for all information providers such as libraries. This is because of its relevance and application to tasks in libraries

and information centres. The potential impact of internet on the public demand for the services and resources of libraries is an issue of critical importance.

Study carried out by Ogunbodede & Oribhabor (2022) conducted a study on undergraduate students' use of digital resources and academic achievement. 1,500 students made up the study's population, which was surveyed descriptively. Only 4% of the students used digital resources daily, according to the findings, indicating that there was little usage of the library's digital resources. The survey found that students used the Internet, e-books, online instructional videos on YouTube, ejournals, and e-newspapers, and that they believed using the library's digital resources positively affected their academic performance. Ikegwuro, (2017) tried to assess the internet utilization by researchers in two selected special libraries in Kaduna state. The findings revealed that the internet services mostly used by academic staff is e-mail services and that the researcher use internet to search and obtain data for research and publication, access e-journals, sending and receiving mails among others.

Use of Electronic Information Resources by Users in Academic Libraries

When any academic library fails to strive with the information resources of its users, besides satisfactory and effective services such library will not be able to delivered. Dauda and Lizette (2020). This study examines the utilization of e-resources at Modibbo Adama University of Technology, (MAUTech) Yola under the auspices of the central library, the Ibrahim Babangida Library. Academics and students are primary users of information resources of any library, hence, their responses towards the utilization of e-resources in the institution have been critically considered in this study. A Mixed method research Design was adopted for the study. A case study approach was employed. The Technology Acceptance Model

(TAM) and Diffusion of Innovation (DoI) theories were used to develop the conceptual framework of this paper. Questionnaires were used as data gathering tools. Academics and students acted as participants. Major findings are lack of sufficient Internet access for academics and students and lack of training and awareness campaigns. Conclusion has shown that e-resources did not impact research and teaching of academics in MAUTech, Yola.

METHODOLOGY

Survey design was used for this study. The use of survey research design is suitable for this work because the study is aimed at surveying the utilization of electronic information resources by user’s in academic libraries in Maiduguri, Borno State. The population of this study comprised of 15,238 registered library users of three (3) academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolitan which include Mohammed Lawan library in college of

Agriculture, Ramat polytechnic library and Ramat library university of Maiduguri. A systematic random sampling technique was employed to realize, the representative sample of the study. The researcher drew a sample size of three hundred and seventy-five (375) using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) formula for determining sample size. The researcher adopted self-designed questionnaire as the instrument for data collection, instrument was subjected to a statistical test of Pre-test r= 0.79. The data collected were analysis using frequency count and percentage was used to present the results.

Data Analysis

A total of three hundred and seventy five (375) copies of the questionnaire were administered to respondents in three selected academic libraries in Borno State. Out of this number 341 (91%) were completed, returned and found usable.

Results Presentation

Research Question One: What is the level of utilization of electronic databases by users’ in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State?

Table 4.1: Level of Utilization of Electronic Databases by User in Academic Libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State, Nigeria n 341

Table with 5 columns: Items, HL, ML, LL, VLL. Rows include utilization levels for information, research, assignment, and teaching/learning, plus a Total Average row.

Response Scale: Keys: High Level (HL); Moderate Level (MD); Low Level (LL) and Very Low Level (VLL)

Table 4.1 shows the level of utilization of e-databases for information, majority

(158;46.3%) indicated high level; while the least (16;4.7%) indicated very low level. This implies that majority of the respondents utilized

of e-database for information in the libraries under study. On the utilization of e-databases for research, majority (166;48.6%) indicated moderate level while the least (21;6.1%) indicated very low level. The result shows that majority of the respondents utilize e-databases for research in the library under study. On utilization of e-databases for assignment, majority (138 ;38.7%) indicated high level

while the least (19;5.5%) indicated very low level. The findings revealed that majority utilize of e-database for assignment. On the utilization of e-databases for teaching/learning, majority (131;38.4%) indicated high level while the least (45;13.1%) indicated very low level. This implies that majority of the respondents, utilize e-electronic database at moderate level.

Research Questions Two: What is the extent of Internet utilization by users' in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State?

Table 4.2 Utilization of Internet by Users in Academic Libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State, Nigeria n 341

Items	HE	ME	LE	VLE
The extent of utilization of Internet for information	135(39.5%)	111(32.5%)	67(19.6%)	28(8.2%)
The extent of utilization of Internet for research/teaching	102(41.2%)	144(42.2%)	69(20.2%)	21(6.1%)
The extent of utilization of Internet for sending/receiving mails	108(31.7%)	135(39.6%)	68(19.9%)	30(8.7%)
The extent of utilization of Internet for social networking	131(38.4%)	112(32.8%)	69(20.2%)	29(8.5%)
Total Average	476/4 119 =34.9	502/4 125.5=36.9	273/4 68.2=20	108/4 27=8

Response Scale: High Extent (HE); Moderate Extent (ME); Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE)

Table 4.2 shows the extent of Internet utilization and users' satisfaction in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State. On the utilization of Internet for information, majority (135;39.3%) indicated high extent; while the least (28;8.2%) indicated very low extent. This implies that majority of the respondents utilize internet for information. On the utilization of Internet for research/teaching, majority (144;42.2%) indicated high extent while the least (21;6.1%) indicated very low extent. The findings revealed that majority of

respondents utilize internet for research teaching purpose. On the utilization of Internet for sending/receiving mails, majority (135;39.6%) indicated high extent while the least (30;8.7%) indicated very low extent. This shows that majority of the respondents utilize internet for sending/receiving mails. On the utilization of Internet for social networking, majority (131;38.4%) indicated high extent while the least (29;8.5%) indicated very low extent. This shows that majority of the respondents, utilize internet at moderate extent in the academic libraries under study.

Research Question Three: What is the extent of use electronic information resources by users in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State?

Table 4.3: Use of Electronic Information Resources by Users in Academic Libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State, Nigeria n 341

Items	HE	ME	LE	VLE
The extent of satisfaction with utilization of e-database for information	128(37.5%)	115(33.7%)	70(20.5%)	28(8.2%)
The extent of satisfaction with utilization of e-databases for research	82(24%)	147(43.1%)	88(25.8%)	24(7%)
The extent of satisfaction with utilization of e-databases for assignment	118(34.6%)	116(34%)	76(22.2%)	31(9%)
The extent of satisfaction with utilization of e-databases for teaching/learning	80(23.4%)	128(37.5%)	84(24.6%)	49(14.3%)
The extent of satisfaction with utilization of Internet for information	146(42.8%)	109(31.9%)	53(15.5%)	33(9.6%)
The extent of satisfaction with utilization of Internet for research	115(33.7%)	121(35.4%)	78(22.8%)	27(7.9%)
The extent of satisfaction with utilization of Internet for assignment	137(40.1%)	107(31.3%)	70(20.5%)	27(7.9%)
The extent of satisfaction with utilization of Internet for teaching/learning	99(29%)	135(39.5%)	66(19.3%)	41(12%)
Total Average	905/8 113.1=33.1	978/8 122.2=35.9	585/8 73.1=21.4	260/8 32.6=9.6

Response Scale: High Extent (HE); Moderate Extent (ME); Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE)

Table 4.3 shows users' satisfaction with electronic information resources in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State. On utilization of e-databases for information, majority (128; 37.5%) indicated high extent; while the least (28;8.2%) indicated very low extent. On satisfaction with utilization of e-databases for research, majority (147;43.1%) indicated moderate extent while the least (24;7%) indicated very low extent. On satisfaction with utilization of e-databases for assignment, majority (118;34.6%) indicated high extent while the least (31;9%) indicated very low extent. On satisfaction with utilization of e-databases for teaching/learning, majority (128;37.5%) indicated high extent while the least (49;14.3%) indicated very low extent. On

satisfaction with utilization of internet for information, majority (146;42.8%) indicated high extent while the least (33;9.6%) indicated very low extent. On satisfaction with utilization of Internet for research, majority (121;35.4%) indicated moderate extent while the least (27;7.9%) indicated very low extents. On satisfaction with utilization of Internet for assignment, majority (137;40.1%) indicated high extent while the least (27;7.9%) indicated very low extent. Finally, on satisfaction with utilization of Internet for teaching/learning, majority, (135;39.5%) indicated moderate extent while the least 41;12%) indicate very low extent. These shows that majority of the respondents are satisfied with electronic information resources at moderate extent in

academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State.

Conclusion

From the findings of this study, the following conclusions have been drawn. The level of utilization of e-databases by users was indicated to moderate extent by majority of the respondents in academic libraries under study. The result on extent of Internet utilization by users' indicated moderate extent in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State. Finally, majority of the users, use electronic information resources at moderate extent in academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State.

Recommendations

In line with the findings, the following recommendation are here by suggested

1. The Managements of academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State should encourage the level of utilization of e-databases by users to high extent
2. Managements of academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State should provide free internet connectivity for users to facilitate searching for information resources at high extent.
3. Management of academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State should provide more electronic information resources to their users to enhance their searching information at high extent.

References

Akuffo, M. N. (2019). Use of electronic resources by students in a premier postgraduate theological University of Ghana. *South African Journal Information Management* 21(1):

Ankrah, E & Acheampong, E.K. (2017). Students' use of electronic resources in University of professional studies, Accra. *Journal of Information Science, Systems and Technology* 1 (2):1126.

Ariffin, M.Y.M. and Bakar, A.A. (2013). *The challenges in the usage of e-journal amongst lecturers at a public university*. 13th International Educational Technology Conference. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 103, 975 – 981.

Atanda, L. A. (2017) Internet Usage and User Satisfaction with Library Services in Federal University, *Journal of Library & Information Science*, 7(3), 1-16

Daramola, C. F. (2016). Perception and utilization of electronic resources by undergraduate students: the case of the Federal University of Technology Library, Akure. *American Journal of Educational Research* 4(5): 366-370.

Dukper, K.B. Sakibu, B. & Arthur, B. (2018). Awareness and utilization of electronic resources by students of Tamale Technical University, Ghana. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Paper 2078. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/2078>.

Edga, A. P. (2020). An assessment on the utilization of electronic resources bachelor of arts in mass communication at the university of Dar es salaam. University of Dar es salaam.

Habiba, U. and Chowdhury, S. (Use of electronic resources and its impact: A study of Dhaka university library users, *The Eastern Librarian*, 23(1):74-90.

Ikegwuro, P. U. (2017) Utilization of Internet Resources/Services by Academic Staff of National Water Resources Institute and Federal College of Forestry Mechanization, Kaduna, Kaduna State. *Advances in Sciences and Humanities*. 3(5) 54-60.

doi: 10.11648/j.ash.20170305.13

- Kumar, G. R. (2016). Awareness and use of digital library resources by faculty members of engineering college libraries in Warangal District Telangana: A study. *International of Research in Library Science*, 2(2), 188-2018
- Kwadzo, G. (2015). Awareness and Usage of Electronic Databases by Geography and Resource Development Information Studies Graduate Students in The University of Ghana” *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal).Paper* 1210. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1210>.
- Mandale, S. R. (2019). E-resource usage in Ayurved Medical College libraries in Maharashtra. *International Journal of Library and Information Studies* 9 (4): 67-73.
- Madondo, T., Sithole, N., & Takainganhamo Chisita, C. (2017). Use of Electronic Information Resources by Undergraduate Students in the Faculty of Management and Administration at Africa University, Mutare, Zimbabwe, Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences, 2(2): 1-12.
- Moyo, L. M. (2004). The virtual patron, Science and Technology Libraries, 25: 185-209.
- Mutani, V. (2016). Utilization of library resources at Saint Augustine University of Tanzania (main campus) Mzumbe University, Accessed online at <http://hdl.handle.net/11192/2068>. Retrieved on 25th October, 2021.
- Nisha, F. & Nanshad, Ali, P. M. (2013). Awareness and use of e-journals by IT Delhi and Delhi University library users’ collection building. *Library and Information Science Research* 32(2), 57-64.
- Obaseki, O., Oye, K. & Mamman, A. (2012). Impact of Electronic Resources on Students Academic Performance. *African journal of library, archives and information sciences*, 27(1), 78-79.
- Ogunbodede, K. F., & Oribhabor, C. B. (2022). Digital resources usage and academic performance of undergraduate students in Nigeria: A case study. *European Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Education*, 3(2), e02213. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30935/ejimed/12491>
- Obiamalu, A.R., Ogungbeni, J.I. and Obuezie, A.C. (2021). Extent of Awareness and Usage of Electronic Databases by Undergraduates in Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Nigeria. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 6(1), 111125.
- Toteng, B., Hoskins, R. and Bell, F. (2013). Use of electronic databases by Law students at the university of Botswana library. *African Journal of Library, Archival and Information science*, 23 (1): 59-74.
- Zarghani, M., Eskrootchi R., Hoseini A. F. Noorishadkam M, Golmohammadi A., and Mostaghaci M. (2015). Virtual Library: An Essential Component of Virtual Education, *Journal of Medical Education and Development*, 10(1): 36-46.